

B chromosomes: the troubles of integration

N. Granada, E. Rebollo, F.J. Sánchez and P. Arana

Departamento de Genética, Universidad Complutense, Madrid (Spain)

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Abstract. Starting with a spontaneous B-A centric fusion found in a natural population of the grasshopper *Eyprepocnemis plorans*, we have obtained different strains carrying the rearrangement in various conditions and doses. Using this material, we have analyzed the meiotic behavior of the translocated chromosome in living cultured spermatocytes, simulating the successive steps of a hypothetical process of integration of a B chromosome into the standard genome via B-A centric fusion. Remarkably, the behavior of fusion heterozygotes, the initial step of the integration process, is much more regular than that of any other configuration, including homozygotes. The reasons for the failure of B chromosome integration into the normal complement by translocation are discussed.

Accessory or “B” chromosomes are dispensable, additional chromosomes appearing in polymorphic state in natural populations of numerous plants and animal species (Beukeboom, 1994). Even though their morphology, behavior, and origin may be very variable, they are generally considered as selfish elements of the genomes, efficiently self-perpetuating due to their particular mechanisms of preferential transmission to the offspring (for review see Camacho et al., 2000, and Camacho, 2004).

The B chromosome polymorphism found in the grasshopper *Eyprepocnemis plorans* is an ancient and complex one. Up to 43 different types of Bs have been found in the Iberian Peninsula (Henriques-Gil et al., 1984; Henriques-Gil and Arana, 1990; Lopez-Leon et al., 1993), and a comparable variation occurs in Moroccan populations (Bakkali et al., 1999).

The polymorphism appears to be engaged in a very dynamic process where new variants continuously arise by mutation from the old ones and may, eventually, substitute them (Henriques-Gil and Arana, 1990). In addition to the classical heterotic and parasitic models (Jones and Rees, 1982), Camacho et al. (1997) proposed a new model for B chromosome maintenance in natural populations of *E. plorans*, based on numerous studies on the polymorphism in Spanish populations. In this third model, near-neutral ancient B variants are replaced by new parasitic Bs arisen by mutation that extend through preferential transmission mechanisms. These mechanisms are subsequently lost along with the harmful effects of the Bs due to the neutralizing influence of the A genome. Neutralized Bs will slowly tend to disappear from the populations due to slight selection against individuals with many B chromosomes and random drift until the whole cycle starts again.

Besides disappearing or being substituted, another possible evolutionary fate for B chromosomes is postulated to be integration into the normal genome, this would lastingly guarantee the survival of the B. Evidences for the integration of B chromosomes as members of the normal complement arise from genetic and molecular analyses of the Y chromosomes of *Drosophila* species, that has been proposed to be, in origin, an accessory that became involved in the sexual system (Hackstein et al., 1996). In another case, the numeric stabilization brought by the acquisition of regular meiosis of the B chromosomes of the haplodiploid wasp *Trypoxylon albitarse* is considered to be a sign of integration (Araújo et al., 2001). Another mechanism for integration has been proposed to be translocation between B chromosomes and members of the normal complement (White, 1973). Especially, whole-arm translocations – centric fusions – may be a good start for integration (Bakkali et al., 2003) as the trivalents formed in meiosis of translocation heterozygotes are theoretically capable to orientate and segregate regularly and hence do not produce semisterility.

A number of different B-A translocations have been found occasionally in samples from natural populations of *Eyprepocnemis plorans* (Henriques-Gil et al., 1983; Cabrero et al., 1987; Lopez-Leon et al., 1991; Bakkali et al., 2003). However, there is no evidence of spreading as all the mutations appeared in heterozygous condition and two individuals with the same translocation

were never found. Therefore, there is an apparent failure of integration that Bakkali et al. (2003) explained by reduction in the fertility of individuals carrying non-centric B-A translocations. However, as these authors acknowledged, this failure of integration is, somehow, unexpected in the case of centric B-A fusions, as a neutral or near-neutral chromosomal rearrangement with regular transmission would have better chances to spread, overcoming the initial high risk of extinction due to random drift.

On the other hand, our previous studies in living cultured spermatocytes of *E. plorans* have revealed that the X chromosome, several types of B chromosomes, and the autosomes have very different dynamic properties and behavior in the process of orientation within the meiotic spindle, and also marked differences in their modes of segregation. This variability between chromosomes is the consequence of adaptation to their particular situation in the genome: the X and the B chromosomes are natural univalents – they have no partner in the first meiotic division – whereas autosomes always form bivalents. As a consequence of chromosomal adaptation to regular transmission, the X univalent, like the main B types are very slow in their movements and undergo very few changes in direction. At anaphase I they segregate undivided in one of the daughter cells (reductional segregation). By contrast, autosomal univalents move very fast, change direction frequently, and show very irregular segregation, including equational division at anaphase I (separation of sister chromatids), migration failure, and spindle collapse (Rebollo and Arana, 1995, 1998, 2000; Rebollo et al., 1998). These characteristics are adequate for bivalent-forming chromosomes, in order to readily correct any possible initial malorientation and achieve the stable bipolar attachment that persists until anaphase I (Rebollo and Arana, 1995; Rebollo et al., 1998).

If two chromosomes possessing very different behavior fuse to form a single structure, there will probably be consequences in meiotic behavior. Moreover, there might be some cytological reasons for the apparent failure of B-A translocations to expand in natural populations. We have addressed these questions within the context of B chromosome evolution, taking advantage of a spontaneous centric B-A fusion, TS10, involving B1 (an old and frequent B chromosome) and the small autosome S10, found in the natural population of Daimuz (DA).

In our study, the behavior of the mutant chromosome was analyzed in a number of different meiotic structures simulating the successive steps of the integration process, as it should be taken into account that the initial rearrangement is just a starting point, and the new chromosome should accomplish successfully a series of different stages until the integration is complete. So, the TS10 compound was analyzed as a single chromosome (a univalent) as part of a heteromorphic bivalent in fusion heterozygotes, as a member of a trivalent formed by a heterozygous bivalent attached to an additional B1 chromosome, and as a homozygous bivalent. The dynamic characteristics of the orientation movements and the modes of segregation were studied in living cultured spermatocytes of grasshopper strains obtained from the original mutant.

In this way, we have checked the chances for an old, well adapted B chromosome to become integrated as a member of the normal genome by reconstructing the successive steps of the process, using the information obtained from the different configurations of the translocation in male meiosis.

Materials and methods

A male carrying a spontaneous chromosome fusion – TS10 – was found in a natural population of the species *Eyprepocnemis plorans* from Daimuz (Valencia, Spain). The translocation involved S10, the second smallest autosome, and the most common and widespread Iberian B chromosome: B1 (Henriques-Gil et al., 1984). This mutant was backcrossed with virgin females from the same population and heterozygous males were selected among the offspring by testicular biopsy. A first group of these heterozygous males was crossed to sister females so as to obtain translocation homozygotes. Those heterozygous males carrying extra free B chromosomes were backcrossed to virgin females separately in order to establish a line with a high frequency of additional loose accessories that could form trivalent structures. The remaining males without extra B chromosomes were also crossed with virgin females from Daimuz as a source of heterozygotes.

The three types of crossings were repeated during five years – one or two generations per year – until a sufficient number of individuals could be analyzed. As all the stocks were segregating, testicular biopsies were performed in every generation, and the males were used as parents

according to their chromosomal constitution.

In addition, translocation heterozygotes were heat treated at 44 ° C for 4

days, as described in Rebollo and Arana (1995) in order to obtain univalents by crossing over failure. In these individuals we could analyze the behavior of the TS10 compound chromosome when it is not attached to the normal S10, and compare them directly.

Living spermatocyte cultures were made following the technique of Nicklas et al. (1982) from testis of young adult males. Chromosome movements were tracked under phase contrast and photographed at regular intervals. Tracks of the chromosomes were obtained from projections of these images as described in Rebollo and Arana (1995). Overall velocities as well as maximum and minimum velocities were scored for each chromosome separately by measuring the distance between successive positions of the correspondent kinetochore. Comparisons between chromosomes were performed by the non-parametrical statistical tests Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn's (Hollander and Wolfe, 1973).

Results

The structure of the translocation

B1 is an acrocentric chromosome with a small euchromatic short arm (Fig. 1). Its size is approximately 45 % of the length of the X chromosome (Figs. 1 and 2). S10 is the second smallest autosome and, apparently, it has no short arm. Its length is approximately 47 % of the X chromosome. Consequently, the translocated TS10 is nearly metacentric (Figs. 1 and 2a). This is a rare condition within the *E. plorans* complement, as all the chromosomes of this species, including the X chromosome and the main B types, are telo- or acrocentric. At phase contrast, each arm of TS10 keeps the chromatin characteristics of the original chromosome: the B arm of TS10 is fainter than the autosomal arm in all the structures where TS10 is involved (see Figs. 3–5 and 6).

Silver staining reveals a single kinetochore (Fig. 2b) so, the counterpart of the translocation event – a small centric fragment – was presumably lost, since it was never seen, even in the original mutant.

This raises the question of which of the two possible kinetochores is the one remaining in TS10 chromosome. This is a crucial issue since kinetochores are responsible for the behavior of chromosomes in the processes of orientation and segregation and, hence, in their transmission efficiency. C-banding of early prophase I bivalents suggests that it is the B1 kinetochore the one included in the translocated chromosome (Fig. 2a). Additional evidence supporting this arises from the dynamic behavior of the TS10 chromosome in living spermatocytes, as it will be addressed later.

Living cell observations

The meiotic behavior of the TS10 chromosome was analyzed in a number of situations: as a univalent, as a heterozygous (heteromorphic) bivalent, as a trivalent – in heterozygotes with an extra B chromosome – and as a homozygous bivalent. In addition to the chromosomes involved in the structural change, the X chromosome was tracked also for comparison, as this natural univalent shows perfectly regular transmission and it has been used for reference in our previous studies (Rebollo and Arana, 1995). In certain cases, autosomal bivalents were also tracked to compare with the behavior of the structures involving TS10 (see Fig. 6).

Univalents

The X univalent in all the cells analyzed in this study behaves just like any other *E. plorans* X chromosome previously reported: it is a static chromosome that shows slow interpolar movements and seldom reorients during prometaphase I, and its segregation at anaphase I is flawlessly reductional (i.e. the chromosome moves undivided to one of the poles). Average, maximum and minimum velocities are shown in Table 1 in relation to other chromosomes of various origins.

At the other extreme, the autosome S10, like all autosomal univalents is much faster and reorients often in prometaphase

I. At metaphase I it acquires amphitelic (mitotic-like) orientation by attaching each chromatid to a different pole (Fig. 7). This leads to a series of segregation irregularities.

As mentioned above, the TS10 chromosome could, in principle, keep either the autosomal or the B1 kinetochore. Univalent dynamics and behavior depend on kinetochore characteristics, and

these are likely to be retained, at least to a certain extent, in the translocated chromosome, so, from the behavior of the TS10 univalent we can infer the origin of its kinetochore.

When the three univalents present in heat treated cells are compared, TS10 behaves like the X chromosome in terms of velocity and frequency of reorientations, and both are clearly different from the S10 autosomal univalent (Tables 1 and 2). This indicates that the TS10 kinetochore belongs to the B1 chromosome, which is as static as the X univalent, rather than to the dynamic autosome S10. Comparisons with B1, X and A chromosomes from the same populations scored in other experiments confirm this assessment (Table 1).

Heterozygotes

Heteromorphic bivalents are like bipartite structures. Consequently, they are capable of bipolar stabilization by opposite tension forces. However, their two kinetochores are of different nature, and this affects their behavior.

Heteromorphic bivalents take longer to achieve bipolarity than normal bivalents, and, in some cases, "flip-flop" reorientations (i.e. orientation reversion after bipolarity) occurs, an event never seen in normal cells. Moreover, congression is impaired and the TS10 bivalent shows broad oscillations between the poles (Fig. 4).

Very often, the TS10 chromosome appears rod-like, not showing any sign of bending at the centromeric region (an indication of attachment to the spindle). It is then possible that this chromosome does not maintain a functional kinetochore fibre all the time.

The velocity of the S10 autosome in heterozygotes is lower than that of the S10 univalent (Table 2). This indicates that the presence of an attached TS10 somewhat hinders the movements of the S10 autosome. Conversely, the TS10 member of the heteromorphic bivalent shows the same velocity as the TS10 univalent.

Despite the defects in orientation, segregation of TS10 heterozygotes is not disastrous (Fig. 7). Yet, in two out of 15 cells, after anaphase separation of S10 and TS10, the latter acquired amphitelic orientation and lagged at the equator. It finally divided equatorially in one of these two cells. In the other cell, TS10 migration failed. Two abnormal cells out of 15 is still a too frequent event to consider segregation of TS10 heterozygotes as regular.

Trivalents

Trivalents form by a chiasmatic terminal or interstitial association between the B1 portion of the TS10 heterozygous bivalent and an additional free B1 chromosome. They are very frequent in individuals with extra B chromosomes. The TS10 trivalent is a rather static structure: reorientations are scarce and the velocities of the TS10, S10 and B members of the trivalent are the lowest found for each chromosome in all the cases studied (Tables 1 and 2).

Quite often, the trivalents adopt a linear configuration, with bipolar attachment of the kinetochores placed at the ends (those of S10 and B1 chromosomes) whereas the TS10 kinetochore lies at the middle of the structure (Fig. 5). Persistence of the linear configuration is the most frequent cause of malsegregation of the trivalent. In six out of eleven cells, TS10 migrated together with either B1 (one cell) or S10 (five cells, Fig. 7). In the latter case, this results in aneuploidy for S10.

Homozygotes

In TS10 homozygotes the bivalent has one chiasma in the autosomal half of the chromosomes. This chiasma can be distal or interstitial, but the behavior is alike. Two ring bivalents with an additional chiasma in the B1 half of TS10 were also scored. TS10 homozygous bivalents are also bipartite structures capable of acquiring bipolarity. In this case, the two kinetochores are identical so, there should not be predominance of one over the other. However, this does not necessarily imply a regular behavior of the bivalent. In fact, TS10 homozygotes show more orientation irregularities than TS10 heterozygotes: reorientations occur in most cells, and perfect congression is never achieved (Fig. 6).

In a first instance, the velocity of TS10 in these bivalents was scored separately for the two members, yielding an almost identical estimation for both chromosomes. Velocities of both TS10 chromosomes were then pooled for the statistical analysis. In homozygotes, the velocity of TS10 is the same as in univalents, but slightly higher than that of heterozygotes (Tables 1 and 2), which is another indication of a higher degree of instability.

Irregularity shows up again in segregation behavior: the two TS10 chromosomes segregated correctly only in three out of nine cells. In approximately half of the other cells (five out of nine)

the whole bivalent was included in one of the poles, which is the most severe type of nondisjunction for a bivalent. In the remaining cell, the whole structure remained at the equator showing no migration at all (Fig. 7). So, despite the equal kinetochores, the behavior of the TS10 homozygous bivalent is clearly more abnormal than that of heterozygous bivalents.

Discussion

The chromosomes

Centric fusions, i.e. whole arm translocations, are one of the chromosomal rearrangements that, in theory, do not entail a high degree of sterility in heterozygotes because trivalents in meiosis have only one way of stabilization in the spindle that coincides with genetically balanced segregation: alternate orientation. They have actually played a role in the evolution of many plant and animal groups, including grasshoppers (Bidau and Mirol, 1988). So, as acknowledged by Bakkali et al. (2003), they are the most favorable starting point for a B chromosome to become integrated into the normal genome. By contrast, the B-A translocation recently described in *E. plorans* by these authors is a reciprocal interchange of terminal fragments (Bakkali et al., 2003). As the same authors concluded, this type of translocations is not a good candidate for integration, as all the possible meiotic configurations necessarily bear a high probability of aneuploidy, either because univalents are formed, or because chiasmata in interstitial regions, i.e. between the centromere and the breakpoint, should occur.

However, despite the favorable characteristics, B-A fusions do not spread in *E. plorans* populations. One explanation for that might be the selfish nature and/or the peculiar mode of transmission of the B chromosome that could impair the behavior of the autosomal part of the compound chromosome. Obviously, a recent B variant still possessing harmful effects could not be integrated in the genome as selection would also operate against the translocated chromosome, likewise, a meiotically irregular B chromosome or a B chromosome with mechanism of accumulation would produce serious disturbances in the transmission of the A member of the translocation. Yet, B1 is, in principle, a good candidate for integration as it is an ancient, near-neutral B chromosome with no accumulation mechanism in the Iberian Peninsula (Henriques-Gil et al., 1982) and, consequently, has no detectable harmful effect in low doses. Meiotically, the B1 univalent is perfectly regular, and its behavior resembles very much that of the X chromosome in male meiosis: reductional division at anaphase I and equational at anaphase II. B1 dynamics at prometaphase I is also like that of the X univalent: both are slow in motion and reorient rarely (Rebollo and Arana, 1995). When two B1 chromosomes are present in the same individual they form bivalents in 57 % of the meiocytes and segregate normally (Henriques-Gil et al., 1982), in the remaining cases the two univalents segregate at random. In female meiosis B1 behavior is similar to that observed in males (Cano et al., 1987).

As S10 is a perfectly normal and regular autosome, the causes of the obviously incompetent transmission of TS10 should be searched in the event of the translocation itself, not in the chromosomes involved. We are only going to consider cytological effects, but it should be kept in mind that B-A translocations may also produce physiological effects. For instance, the B-A translocation described by Cabrero et al. (1987) in *E. plorans*, triggers the activation of a latent nucleolar organizing region in the B chromosome. Effects like this may clearly have an impact on the long term fate of the rearrangement.

The rearrangement

The first step in the sequence of integration is structural heterozygosity. In TS10 heterozygotes, B1 appears as a member of a bivalent, this is, in principle, an advantage for B transmission as bipartite structures can be stabilized in the spindle by opposite tension forces, ensuring 1:1 segregation. However, B1 is already very regular as a univalent, actually, it is slightly more efficient than the TS10 heterozygous bivalent that showed few cases of abnormal segregation (see Fig. 7). This small disadvantage of the heterozygous bivalent could be attributed to the disparity of its two kinetochores. Inequality between kinetochores is evident from the fact that, in most of the orientation movements, the S10 kinetochore leads while the TS10 kinetochore seems to passively trail. This may be the source of the relative instability of the TS10 heterozygous bivalent, revealed by the broad interpolar oscillations and by the occasional incidence of orientation reversion, the so called flip-flop reorientations, that never occur in normal

bivalents. Moreover, the lack of bending at the centromere of the TS10 chromosome during long periods of prometaphase I indicates that its kinetochore is not properly attached to the spindle and opposing tension to the S10 kinetochore (Fig. 4). This may be due either to a deficiency in TS10 kinetochore or to the fact that the bulk of decondensed B chromatin is hindering the interaction between this kinetochore and the microtubules. As metacentric chromosomes do not occur in *E. plorans*, we cannot compare the behavior of TS10 with that of normal bivalents of the complement.

An incompetent TS10 kinetochore may also be the cause of the dramatic failure in segregation of TS10 trivalents. The behavior of trivalents is important since in the natural populations where B-A chromosomal translocations occur, the frequency of B chromosomes can be quite high (around 40 % in both populations of Daimuz, Spain [Henriques-Gil et al., 1982], and Smir, Morocco [Bakkali et al., 1999]). Thus, during the process of spreading, it is very likely that some individuals bearing the translocation possess additional free B chromosomes. As B1 is the most frequent B chromosome in Daimuz, in all the individuals analyzed the extra B was always B1. Two B1 chromosomes in the same cell form one chiasma in meiosis with a high frequency (57 %, Henriques-Gil et al., 1982), in our experiments, the frequency of chiasmata is even higher since virtually all cells of TS10 heterozygotes with extra B1 chromosomes showed a trivalent, either with a proximal or a distal chiasma between the B chromosome homologous regions. So, if a fusion is to survive within the population, it should also be efficient in transmission in these circumstances.

TS10 fusion significantly fails in this new step: in almost half of the cases, S10 and TS10 migrate to the same pole at anaphase I, producing aneuploid cells for the S10 autosome (see Figs. 5 and 7). The reason for this migration failure could be the linear configuration often attained by the trivalent. Linear configurations occur because the TS10 kinetochore remains inactive trapped between the two extreme S10 and B1 kinetochores. Again, this may be favored by the relative incompetence of the TS10 kinetochore. As a consequence of linear orientation, the length of the trivalent could be excessive for the spindle to separate its elements. However, S10 is one of the smallest members of the complement of *E. plorans* and the trivalent does not appear to be extremely long even when the association between B1 and TS10 is distal (Fig. 5). Impairment of segregation due to an excessive length of the structure would rather occur in B-A translocations involving longer autosomes. We rather support the idea that, after release and migration of one of the chromosomes to the pole, the pulling force exerted on the structure drops, the inactive TS10 stays attached to the other chromosome by residual cohesion (Suja et al., 1999) and is passively dragged to the opposite pole.

Homozygosity is the final step in the process of integration; theoretically, any mutation that passed the previous stages should have achieved a very stable situation, making up a bivalent structure, fulfilling all the requirements to orientate and segregate regularly. However, the TS10 homozygous bivalent is the most unstable configuration of the translocation. This fact obviously eliminates all the possible expectations of success for the integration of the B chromosome. Again, the defect seems to reside in the kinetochore of TS10. This time, irregularity cannot be attributed to inequality of kinetochores as both are necessarily identical.

In summary, among all the structures in which the TS10 chromosome can be involved, heterozygous bivalents are the most competent for transmission, followed by the TS10 univalents, the trivalents and, finally, the homozygous bivalents (Fig. 7). According to this situation, there are several possible reasons to account for the problems of integration:

E First of all, it is possible to think that the B1 kinetochore is not suitable to be an element of a complex structure because it is a chromosome adapted to univalency and it has developed a strategy consisting in slow movements and scarce reorientations. This is unfit for a normal chromosome of the A complement since for bivalent forming chromosomes it is advantageous to readily correct the initial malorientations and achieve bipolarity. This is why they evolved kinetochores that move fast and reorient frequently (Rebollo et al., 1998). However, in bivalents formed by two normal B1 chromosomes, the B1 kinetochore works normally both in males and females so, the irregularities of TS10 cannot be fully attributable to the nature of B1 kinetochore.

One could alternatively think that the functionality of the TS10 kinetochore has been damaged in the process of translocation as the breakpoint lies at or near this region. This is supported by the slightly more irregular behavior of TS10 compared to B1. Another sign of abnormality of the

TS10 kinetochore is its increased doubleness in late prometaphase I compared to the remaining chromosomes (unpublished data). Doubleness of sister kinetochores before bipolar stabilization in the meiosis I spindle is a source of instability as it favors amphitelic orientation, with all its adverse consequences (Rebollo and Arana, 1995, 1998; Rebollo et al., 1998). However, it should be noticed that if the TS10 kinetochore is actually impaired, the extent of the damage should be moderate, as both the segregation of univalents and heterozygous bivalents is rather correct.

Another factor to take into account is the difference in chromatin condensation between autosomes and B chromosomes. B1, like the X chromosome of *E. plorans*, is allocyclic in meiosis. This is evident in the fainter aspect under phase contrast of the B1 chromatin in all the TS10 configurations. Around the area of the breakpoint in the centromeric region of TS10, the two types of chromatin are in close contact, which may alter the structure of the chromosome and somehow disrupt the functionality of the kinetochore.

Finally, it is noteworthy that the dynamic meiotic behavior of chromosome TS10 does not vary remarkably between the different configurations. By contrast, both the velocity and the frequency of reorientations of S10 greatly decrease in bivalents and trivalents compared to S10 univalent. In general, it appears that, in hybrid structures, the slowest chromosome determines the velocity of the movements. So, in both types of bivalents it is chromosome TS10 the one dictating the dynamic behavior. Whereas, in trivalents, it is B1, just slightly slower than TS10, the chromosome imposing velocity limits. This explains why trivalents are the structures showing the slowest velocity for both S10 and TS10 chromosomes.

It is then possible that if the TS10 kinetochore had been that of the S10 chromosome, the behavior of the translocation would have been different, and more similar to that of a normal autosomal bivalent. Yet, this does not guarantee regularity nor success in integration since other possible effects like a potential kinetochore damage, heterogeneity of the chromatin around the breakpoint and shielding of the microtubule attachment of the TS10 kinetochore by the B chromatin would not disappear.

So, in our simulation of the process of integration of a B chromosome into the normal genome through B-A centric fusions, the first and theoretically most difficult step, the primary mutation, is the best performing configuration of the translocation. Whereas, the final stage, when most problems are supposed to have been overcome, is the most irregular. This reveals the difficulty of making predictions about the future of such a chromosomal mutation only from the data of heterozygotes. Our work also reveals that, as chromosomes are adapted to their particular role in the genomes, changes that are in principle irrelevant – a genetically balanced rearrangement like centric fusion – may pointedly alter their structure and function and totally prevent a way of chromosomal evolution.

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Fig. 1. Structure of the TS10 centric fusion. The resulting TS10 chromosome is nearly metacentric.

Fig. 2. (a) C-banding of a TS10 heterozygous bivalent at early diplotene. The centromere of TS10 appears to be that of chromosome B1. (b) Silver staining of the heterozygous bivalent of TS10 at prometaphase I. In this case, the TS10 chromosome is bent at the centromeric region, with its kinetochore (double arrowhead) apparently pulling opposite to the S10 kinetochore (arrowhead).

Fig. 3. Tracking of a TS10 univalent in prometaphase I. Times in minutes on the lower left corner of the prints. The TS10 univalent (arrowhead) is stabilized amphitelicly at the equator of the cell from the beginning of the observation, and lags at anaphase I (222 min print), provoking spindle collapse (252 min print). Note the difference in condensation between the autosomal and the B chromatin (16 min print). Bar = 10 μ m.

Fig. 4. Tracking of a TS10 heterozygous bivalent. The bivalent is undergoing broad inter-polar movements including reorientations (0 and 58 min prints) while normal bivalents are perfectly congressed. The S10 chromosome leads the movement. Note the difference in condensation between the autosomal and B regions of TS10. Transient linearity (82 min print) is followed by acquisition of bipolarity (145 min print) and correct segregation at anaphase I (190 min print). Bar = 10 μ m.

Fig. 5. Tracking of a TS10 trivalent. Linear configuration is maintained throughout prometaphase, S10 kinetochore (bottom arrowhead) and B1 kinetochore (top arrowhead) pulling, whereas the TS10 kinetochore (arrowhead at the middle) is trapped between them. At anaphase I (486 min print), S10 does not detach from TS10 and both chromosomes migrate to the lower pole. Bar = 10 μ m.

Fig. 6. (a) Tracking of a TS10 homozygous bivalent and a normal autosomal bivalent in the same cell. The TS10 homozygous bivalent shows one interstitial chiasma in the S10 half of the chromosomes (see 76 min print). The differential condensation between A and B chromatin is evident in most prints. The autosomal bivalent tracked is the long one with a distal chiasma situated on the left of the spindle in 224 min and 259 min prints. The congression of the TS10 bivalent is severely impaired. The TS10 bivalent shows broad interpolar trips and two reorientations (56 and 224 min prints). At anaphase I (285 min print), the whole bivalent migrates to the upper pole. Bar = 10 μ m. (b) Graph showing the position of the chromosomes versus time. The upper and lower continuous lines represent the position of the spindle poles and the straight line at the middle represents the position of the equator. Note the maintenance of bipolarity with small oscillations around the equator of the normal bivalent.

ANAPHASE I SEGREGATION

Fig. 7. Modes of anaphase I segregation of the chromosomes involved in the different configurations of the TS10 translocation. Number of living cells scored for each segregation indicated below. a equational segregation, b migration failure, c spindle collapse.

Table 1. Prometaphase velocities in m/min and frequencies of reorientation movements of the chromosomes analyzed in the different TS10 structures. Last three rows correspond to scores from other experiments where the X, B1 and autosomal univalents from Daimuz population were studied.

	Univalents				Heterozygotes				Trivalents				Homozygotes			
	Max.	Min.	Mean	Average reorientations	Max.	Min.	Mean	Average reorientations	Max.	Min.	Mean	Average reorientations	Max.	Min.	Mean	Average reorientations
TS10	0.94	0.01	0.20	1.5	0.76	0.01	0.17	1.11	0.51	0.01	0.10	0.5	0.63	0.03	0.21	0.66
S10	1.18	0.03	0.46	6.125	1.6	0.01	0.21	1.11	0.86	0.01	0.13	0.5				
X	0.45	0.01	0.16	0.625	0.69	0.01	0.14	0.11	0.47	0.02	0.14	0.5	0.96	0.03	0.16	0.33
B1									0.74	0.01	0.11	0.5				
X DA	0.38	0.05	0.16	0.44												
B1 DA	0.40	0.04	0.16	0.55												
A DA	1.05	0.13	0.48	4.25												

Table 2. Results of Dunn's multiple range tests for the comparisons of the overall velocities of chromosomes TS10 and S10 in the different configurations of translocation. Previous Kruskal-Wallis tests yielded significant differences between configurations ($H = 69.18$, $P \neq 0.001$ for TS10, and $H = 83.71$, $P \neq 0.001$ for S10).

Chromosome TS10 ^a				Chromosome S10 ^a		
Configuration	heterozygotes	homozygotes	trivalents	Configuration	heterozygotes	trivalents
univalents	NS	NS	*	univalents	*	*
heterozygotes	homozygotes	NS	*	heterozygotes		*
			*			

^a * = $P < 0.05$; NS = nonsignificant differences.